

Comparative analysis of postoperative results of various methods of treatment of inguinal hernias

Adlet Mendybayev¹, Alexandr Fursov¹, Irina Volchkova¹, Aruzhan Borankulova², Yerzhan Kuspayev³

¹Department of Surgical Diseases, Astana Medical University, 010000 Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan; ²Department of Medical Sciences, Nazarbayev University, 010000 Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan; ³Department of Surgical Diseases, Astana Medical University, 010000 Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan

Abstract

To assess and compare the long-term postoperative complications, postoperative pain incidences, and hernia recurrence rates following surgery for inguinal hernias using different surgical approaches, namely transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP), TAPP with the internal ring suturing (TAPP-IRS), Liechtenstein technique, and Shouldice technique. This study is a multicentre clinical trial that involves 302 patients ranging from 18 to 74 years old (with an average age of 55.4±10.6 years). Among the participants, there were 49 women (16.2%) and 253 men (83.8%), all diagnosed with primary inguinal hernias. Out of the total, 216 patients (71.5%) had a normal body mass index, 77 patients (25.5%) were overweight, and 9 patients (7%) were obese. The interventions utilized in the study included open techniques such as the Liechtenstein technique (121 patients) and the Shouldice technique (27 patients), as well as the laparoscopic technique using the TAPP approach (98 patients), with 56 of them undergoing the modified procedure involving internal ring suturing. The study aimed to assess the frequency and severity of chronic postoperative pain and postoperative complications such as testicular edema, infiltration, sup-puration, and urinary retention within a year and the recurrence rate of an inguinal hernia within two years. The occurrence and intensity of chronic pain syndrome were moderate, with no significant differences observed between the different surgical approaches. The overall hernia recurrence rate during the two-year follow-up period was 2.8%, and no significant differences were observed among the surgical methods used except the TAPP-IRS method. Notably, the TAPP-IRS subgroup had no reported cases of recurrence. The patients' weight was identified as the most significant risk factor, followed by the choice of intervention technique. It is important to consider the TAPP-IRS subgroup, which exhibited no instances of recurrence. The type of intervention had a minimal impact on the risk of recurrence and other post-operational complications, primarily due to limitations in open surgical procedures and the technique of the TAPP-IRS. During the postoperative period for indirect inguinal hernia repair, the laparoscopic method results in a lower incidence and less severe postoperative pain at one month compared to open hernioplasty. However, by the 12-month mark, the pain subsides, and both methods exhibit comparable characteristics. *Clin Ter 2025; 176 (6):708-716 doi: 10.7417/CT.2025.5287*

Keywords: *inguinal hernia, surgical treatment, internal ring suturing, transabdominal pre-peritoneal surgery, open surgery; Shouldice*

Introduction

A hernia can be defined as an abnormal protrusion of an organ or tissue caused by the structural vulnerability of the wall of the surrounding cavity (Townsend et al, 2012). The most common type of hernia is an inguinal hernia. Inguinal hernias are one of the most common surgical problems requiring intervention, and they always remain a pressing issue for the medical community. The use of various treatment methods and the search for the optimal way to manage inguinal hernias have always been the subject of discussion and research. Patients expect effective and safe treatment methods from surgeons, which will provide them with quick rehabilitation and eliminate further risks. The main objective of the scientific study was to evaluate and compare long-term postoperative complications, the frequency of postoperative pain, and the frequency of recurrence of inguinal hernias after the use of different surgical approaches. The study was conducted in the form of a multicentre clinical trial with the aim of finding out which of the methods of treatment of inguinal hernias are the most effective and reliable for patients. There are two common repair methods for inguinal hernias: open procedures and laparoscopic procedures (Shakil et al, 2020). However, there are no uniform recommendations in favour of one method over another (open or laparoscopic). Various surgical techniques have been thoroughly investigated, including open techniques such as Lichtenstein and Shouldice as well as laparoscopic approaches using the transabdominal pre-abdominal (TAPP) method, including the modified TAPP-IRS method (Decker et al, 2019; Sun et al, 2020). The results of the study can contribute to the selection of the optimal method of treatment of inguinal hernias, which will satisfy the needs of patients and contribute to their rapid recovery and general well-being. In addition, this study can make an influential contribution to the development of surgery and improve the standards of treatment for inguinal hernias for future generations of patients.

Treatment of inguinal hernias can include various methods that have been developed and improved over the years by doctors. This method does not have a specific developer and is developed using modern technologies. The TAPP technique also uses laparoscopy to access the inguinal

Correspondence: Adlet Mendybayev, email: mendybayevadlet9@gmail.com

canal but involves creating a mesh and closing the axillary canal. TAPP with an internal annular suture (TAPP-IRS) is a modified version of the TAPP technique that includes an additional internal annular suture to strengthen the inguinal canal (Gong and Liu, 2019; Fernando et al, 2019). Each of these methods has its advantages and disadvantages and can be chosen depending on the individual characteristics of the patient and the recommendations of the doctor. The laparoscopic approach offers two methods: transabdominal extraperitoneal (TEP) and transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP), both using mesh to reinforce the area (Castro et al, 2022; Schmitz et al, 2019; Tam et al, 2019). Although these laparoscopic procedures have gained popularity and are widely used in hernia repair, open operations such as the Lichtenstein technique and the Shouldice technique are still widely used (Wolak et al, 2022). The laparoscopic approach to hernia repair is considered minimally invasive and involves smaller incisions compared to traditional open procedures (El Aal Sultan et al, 2022). This method offers a number of advantages, including being the easiest to perform, improved quality of life for patients, the fastest recovery time, less postoperative pain, and less morbidity or complications compared to open surgery (Chowbey et al, 2006). The most common complications after inguinal hernia surgery are testicular edema, infiltration, suppuration, and urinary retention (Vu et al, 2019). The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of both laparoscopic and open surgeries, taking into account postoperative complications, hernia recurrence, and pain. Postoperative pain is a common phenomenon after surgery, which is usually expected during the first few days and tends to gradually decrease with the use of analgesics (Mellert et al, 2019; Sun, 2007). Monitoring postoperative pain is critical because it directly affects morbidity, healthcare costs, and the overall quality of life of patients.

Thus, the assessment and management of postoperative pain are important aspects of surgical practice, as are postoperative complications and recurrences. Compared to other works, the long-term orientation of this research determines its relevance and scientific significance. This study evaluated different surgical approaches, including TAPP, TAPP with an internal suture ring (TAPP-IRS), the Lichtenstein technique, and the Shouldice technique. The main goal of this study was to compare long-term postoperative complications and the effectiveness of operations for inguinal hernias using the above methods. All of these techniques aim to repair the inguinal hernia and prevent recurrence, and development and improvement continue to improve treatment outcomes and reduce postoperative risks.

Materials and Methods

The study design is a prospective multicentre clinical study from January 2018 to September 2021 in Astana, Kazakhstan. The Clinical Trial Centre in Astana, which includes multidisciplinary clinics with surgical departments, served as the research location. The following clinics were involved in the study: Multidisciplinary Regional Hospital No. 2, City Multidisciplinary Hospital No. 2, and City Multidisciplinary Hospital No. 3 in Astana. These clinics are equal in terms

of experience. Multiple surgeons performed the operations, with standardized methodological and technical approaches used for all groups.

The protocol was approved by the medical centre's Ethics Committee. In accordance with the World Medical Association Declaration, patients' safety, and well-being were protected throughout the study. Informed consent was required to be obtained from each participant before study enrolment. Before patients were discharged from the hospital, a thorough clinical examination was conducted, ensuring compliance with the relevant Diagnosis and Treatment Protocols. Additionally, outpatient follow-up examinations were carried out in accordance with the local ethics committee protocols (REC/IRB) to monitor the patient's recovery and progress after the hernioplasty procedure. This systematic approach aimed to provide comprehensive and standardized care for the patients throughout their treatment journey.

All patients admitted to the hospital were enrolled in the study except those who did not fit the inclusion criteria stated in the section below. Patients were not allocated to the groups for results alleviation. Patients had an opportunity to choose their own method of hernia repair considering the surgeon's consultation. The preoperative preparation for the patients followed current protocols based on the latest standards for diagnosis and treatment. Patients undergoing elective procedures typically underwent preoperative preparation as outpatients, meaning they did not require overnight hospital stays before the surgery. On the other hand, for emergency operations, a series of measures were taken to address any impairments in vital functions that were identified upon admission. These measures aimed to stabilize and correct any issues with the patient's vital functions before proceeding with the emergency surgery. The preoperative preparation ensured that patients were in the best possible condition for a successful surgical intervention and optimal outcomes. The choice of anesthetic support for each patient was made based on their individual condition, age, body weight, overall health status, and the presence of any concomitant diseases or dysfunctions in organs and systems. It is important to note that laparoscopic hernioplasty was not utilized in emergency surgical interventions. Furthermore, the Lichtenstein technique was avoided in young individuals to prevent potential adverse effects on their reproductive function. When examining the correlation between the body weight level and the hernioplasty technique, it is important to highlight that the Shouldice method was not used for obese patients. Instead, most obese patients underwent hernia repair using the TAPP technique.

Overall, the selection of surgical techniques and anesthesia management was tailored to each patient's unique circumstances to ensure the best possible outcome and minimize potential risks. For open surgeries such as Lichtenstein and Shouldice techniques, spinal anesthesia was implemented, while for TAPP and TAPP-IRS general anesthesia with intubation was implemented. Local infiltration anesthesia was employed in instances involving individual cases with a heightened susceptibility to anesthesia complications (such as intubation), heart attacks, thromboembolism, and similar issues among elderly patients who had significant underlying health conditions affecting their cardiovascular

and respiratory systems. Participants' eligibility was based on these criteria:

- age over 18 years;
- diagnosis of indirect inguinal hernia;
- undergoing open hernia repair by either the Lichtenstein or Shouldice techniques or laparoscopic surgery using the TAPP and TAPP-IRS.

Patients that had hernias in other locations besides the groin, had inguinal hernia recurrence, and underwent surgical interventions using different methods of hernia repair were excluded from this study.

The following procedures were assessed: TAPP, TAPP-IRS, Lichtenstein, and Shouldice technique. TAPP is a minimally invasive laparoscopic surgical technique used to repair inguinal hernias. TAPP surgery involves making small incisions in the abdominal wall, through which a laparoscope and surgical instruments are inserted. The surgeon then creates a preperitoneal space and places a mesh prosthesis to reinforce the weakened area and repair the hernia (Bittner et al, 2011).

TAPP-IRS is also a minimally invasive laparoscopic procedure, but in comparison with regular TAPP, this approach involves internal ring suturing. During a TAPP-IRS procedure, the surgeon performs a laparoscopic approach, creating small incisions in the abdominal wall. A laparoscope and surgical instruments are inserted to access the preperitoneal space. In addition to placing a mesh prosthesis to reinforce the weakened area and repair the hernia, a unique feature of TAPP-IRS is the internal ring suturing (Li et al, 2022).

A Lichtenstein repair of a hernia is a type of open surgical procedure that involves a tension-free mesh repair. During the surgery, the direct hernia is separated from the cord structures and then gently pushed back into the abdominal cavity. The defect or weakness in the abdominal wall is then closed using sutures, and a mesh is placed over the repaired area to bridge the defect. The mesh serves to provide additional support and reinforcement to prevent the hernia from recurring. This method of repair is considered effective and is commonly used to treat direct hernias (Sakorafas, 2001).

Shouldice repair is a specialized surgical approach used for the repair of inguinal hernias. During Shouldice surgery, the hernia is repaired by sewing together the different anatomical layers in the groin area, creating a strong and natural repair without the use of mesh. The procedure is performed in four layers using a permanent suture, providing excellent durability and a low recurrence rate for patients undergoing inguinal hernia repair. Shouldice surgery is considered an effective option for patients who prefer a non-mesh repair or have specific medical reasons for avoiding mesh implants (Chan and Chan, 2006).

In laparoscopic hernioplasty, internal ring suturing, a newly invented technique, emerged as a primary approach to prevent recurrent hernias. This suturing technique was employed when the diameter of the internal ring was larger than 3 cm. The suturing process took place before the application and fixation of the mesh implant, ensuring a secure and effective repair of the hernia site. By suturing the internal ring, the surgeon reinforces the weakened area and reduces the risk of hernia recurrence, making it a valuable step in the TAPP procedure. In both endoscopic hernioplasty (TAPP technique) and the Lichtenstein technique, a low-density

polypropylene mesh was the preferred choice. This type of mesh is known for its ability to adapt well to the tissues of the inguinal region and easily fit with the TAPP approach. Furthermore, the mesh elicits minimal or no noticeable reaction from the surrounding tissues, reducing the risk of adverse responses to a foreign body.

The statistical analysis of the study results was conducted using SPSS version 20.0 software. To compare frequencies between different groups or categories, the researchers employed statistical tests such as Pearson's chi-square test and Fisher's two-tailed exact test. Pearson's chi-square test is used to analyse the association between two categorical variables and determine if they are significantly related. It assesses whether there is a significant difference in the expected and observed frequencies in the data. Fisher's two-tailed exact test, also used for categorical data, is used when dealing with small sample sizes or when the chi-square test assumptions are not met. It provides an alternative method to determine if there is a significant association between two categorical variables. For the continuous variables in the study one-way ANOVA.

Moreover, the study aimed to assess the influence of various risk factors on the development of long-term complications. To achieve this, multiple-factor analysis (also known as multiple logistic regression) was employed. Multiple-factor analysis allows researchers to identify and quantify the contribution of multiple independent variables (risk factors) to the occurrence of a particular outcome (long-term complications in this case).

Results

The study involved 302 patients aged between 18 and 74 years, with an average age of 55.4 ± 10.6 years. Among these participants, there were 49 women (16.2%) and 253 men (83.3%). To assess the subjects' body weight, the researchers utilized the up-to-date classification provided by the World Health Organization (WHO) (2010). This classification allowed them to determine the body mass index (BMI) in kg/m^2 for each participant. According to these criteria, the classifications were as follows:

1. Underweight: $\text{BMI} < 18.5$.
2. Normal weight: $18.5 \leq \text{BMI} < 24.9$.
3. Overweight: $25 \leq \text{BMI} < 29.9$.
4. Obese: $30 \leq \text{BMI} \leq 34.9$.
5. Severe obesity: $\text{BMI} \geq 35 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$.

By using this BMI classification, the researchers were able to analyse the distribution of subjects based on their body weight. In this research, a total of 216 (71.5%) subjects had a normal body mass index, 77 (25.5%) were overweight, and 9 (7%) were obese. The subjects enrolled were distributed by age category and BMI (Tables 1 and 2)

Lichtenstein technique (121 patients) and the Shouldice technique (27 patients), as well as the laparoscopic technique using the TAPP approach (98 patients), with 56 of them undergoing the modified procedure (Table 3).

During the follow-up period, the patients were examined specifically, either during appointments with the researcher or at their place of residence, four times a year. This systematic and regular follow-up allowed for thorough monitoring

Table 1. Distribution of subjects by age category and BMI

Age	Body weight status							
	Healthy		Increased		Obesity		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
18-35	3	23.0	9	69.2	1	7.7	13	4.3
35-50	47	63.5	25	33.8	2	2.7	74	24.5
51-65	137	75.7	38	20.9	6	3.3	181	59.9
66-74	29	85.3	5	14.7	0	0.0	34	11.2
Total	216	71.5	77	25.5	9	2.9	302	100

Source: compiled by the authors.

Table 2. Distribution of subjects by the hernioplasty technique used and body weight level

Type of hernioplasty	Body weight status							
	Healthy		Increased		Obesity		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Shouldice	24	11.1	2	2.6	1	11.1	27	8.94
Liechtenstein	112	51.8	7	9	2	22.2	121	40.01
TAPP	51	23.6	43	55.9	4	44.4	98	16.89
TAPP-IRS	29	13.5	25	32.5	2	22.2	56	9.6
Total	216	100	77	100	9	100	302	100

Source: compiled by the authors.

Table 3. The average prospective follow-up duration for each technique

Type of hernioplasty	Shouldice	Liechtenstein	TAPP	TAPP-IRS	P-value
Mean of follow-up duration (in years)	2.4±0.5	2.2±0.4	2.1±0.3	1.8±0.2	0.065

Source: compiled by the authors.

of the patient's progress and the assessment of the long-term success of the different hernioplasty techniques employed in the study.

In the early postoperative period in 18 (5.96%) clinical cases developed complications. The study observed an excess frequency of complications in hernioplasty among patients who were overweight and obese. In other words, patients with higher body weight levels experienced more complications following the surgery compared to those with lower body weight levels. The study has identified a significantly high complication rate ($p=0.074$) associated with non-laparoscopic hernioplasty methods in individuals who are overweight and obese. Specifically, when using the Shouldice technique, three patients with elevated BMI experienced a total of 4 complications. Moreover, when performing hernioplasty according to the Liechtenstein technique, from all 7 patients with high BMI, 6 of them developed complications with overall 18 complication cases. In other words, the incidence of patients experiencing complications in the overweight and obese group was high. Laparoscopic techniques have been found to be associated with a significantly lower incidence of early complications in the postoperative period. In the TAPP group, the cumulative frequency of early complications was 19.38%. Interestingly, this frequency was not affected by the presence of excess

BMI (overweight or obesity) compared to individuals with normal BMI. In the TAPP-IRS group, there was only one case of complications observed in patients with increased body mass. This single case accounted for 1.78% of the total group of patients and 3.7% of the corresponding subgroup. The findings suggest that laparoscopic techniques, particularly TAPP and TAPP-IRS, offer a favourable outcome with a reduced risk of early complications, even in patients with higher body mass indices.

When comparing the overall complication rates between non-laparoscopic hernioplasty methods and TAPP (including TAPP-IRS), the study found that in the first case, the complication rate was 14.9%, while in the second case, it was 6.3%. The statistical analysis using the one-way ANOVA test indicated a significant difference between the two groups, with a p-value of 0.029. This means that TAPP and TAPP-IRS had a lower overall complication rate compared to non-laparoscopic methods. Further analysis was conducted based on the patient's BMI levels. In the subgroup without excess BMI, the complication rates for non-laparoscopic methods and TAPP were also significant ($p=0.034$). The p-value was less than 0.05, suggesting that there were significant differences in complication rates between these two groups. However, in the subgroup of patients with increased BMI and obesity, the complication rates were 62.7% and

6.9%, respectively. The one-way ANOVA test ($p=0.00012$) indicated a highly significant difference in complication rates between non-laparoscopic methods and TAPP in this subgroup. In summary, the study found that TAPP, including TAPP-IRS, had a lower overall complication rate compared to non-laparoscopic hernioplasty methods. The difference in complication rates was more pronounced in patients with increased BMI and obesity, where TAPP demonstrated a significantly lower complication rate. In patients without excess BMI, the difference in complication rates between non-laparoscopic methods and TAPP was significant (Figure 1, Table 4).

In this study, authors evaluated the occurrence and severity of chronic pain syndrome experienced by patients. Chronic postoperative pain refers to pain that persists for more than three months after the surgery (Mellert et al, 2019; Sun, 2007). The authors measured the frequency and intensity of the pain experienced by patients to understand the impact of the hernioplasty procedure on their long-term pain outcomes. The study found that the incidence and severity of chronic pain syndrome were moderate, and in most cases, there were no significant differences between different groups of patients who underwent hernioplasty. After one month, the average incidence of chronic pain for the entire group

Fig 1. Frequency and structure of complications in early postoperative period depending on the body mass weight status. Note: numbers on the y-axis represent the number of the cases, while the x-axis represents the types of complications. Source: compiled by the authors.

Table 4. Frequency of different postoperative complications for groups with normal BMI and high BMI for each method of hernioplasty in the early postoperative period

Complication type	Shouldice				Lichtenstein				TAPP				TAPP-IRS			
	Normal BMI		Over-weight and obese		Normal BMI		Over-weight and obese		Normal BMI		Over-weight and obese		Normal BMI		Over-weight and obese	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Swelling of testicles	14	25.92	2	50	37	28.46	6	33.33	5	45.45	4	50	1	50	1	100
Seroma formation	8	14.81	1	25	26	20	2	11.11	3	27.27	2	25	0		0	
Infiltration	12	22.22	0	0	21	16.15	3	16.67	0	0	2	25	1	50	0	
Suppuration	9	16.67	0	0	24	18.46	4	22.22	1	9.09	0	0	0		0	
Urinary retention	11	20.37	1	25	22	16.92	3	16.67	2	18.18	0	0	0		0	
Total	54		4		130		18		11		8		2		1	

Source: compiled by the authors.

Table 5. The occurrence rate and severity of pain syndrome in patients in terms of the hernioplasty technique

Type of hernioplasty	Examination period					
	1 month			12 months		
	Number of patients with pain syndrome	% of total hernioplasty group	Severity of the pain syndrome by VAS (if any)	Number of patients with pain syndrome	% of total hernioplasty group	Severity of the pain syndrome by VAS (if any)
Shouldice, n=27	8	29.6	3.5 (2.5-4.5)	4	14.8	2.3 (2-3)
Liechtenstein, n=121	32	26.4	3.3 (2.3-3.7)	17	14	1.9 (1.5-2.3)
TAPP, n=98	17	17.3	2.3 (2-2.7)	6	6.1	2.1 (1.8-2.3)
TAPP-IRS, n=56	2	3.6	2.1 (2-2.3)	0	0	-
Total, n=302	59	19.5	-	27	8.9	-

Source: compiled by the authors.

was 19.5%, which decreased to 8.9% after 12 months. The severity of chronic pain, as measured by the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), was within the range of 2-5 in the first case (one month after surgery) and 2-3 in the second case (12 months after surgery). Interestingly, a significant difference in the incidence of chronic pain was observed between two specific surgical techniques: open hernioplasty using the Liechtenstein technique and laparoscopic hernioplasty using the TAPP approach. The Pearson's chi-square test ($\chi^2=4.221$) with a p-value of 0.00032 indicated a significant difference in chronic pain incidence between these two groups. This suggests that patients undergoing open hernioplasty using the Liechtenstein technique may have a higher incidence of chronic pain compared to those undergoing laparoscopic hernioplasty with the TAPP approach (Table 5).

Indeed, the absence of any reported cases of pain syndrome after TAPP-IRS in the long-term period is a notable observation from the study. This indicates that TAPP-IRS was highly successful in preventing chronic pain in patients who underwent the procedure. The lack of reported pain syndrome after TAPP-IRS suggests that the internal ring suturing technique used in the surgery was effective in reinforcing the inguinal region and reducing the risk of postoperative pain. The internal ring suturing likely played a crucial role in preventing the hernia from recurring, which is often a significant contributor to chronic pain in hernia repair patients.

The study reports a low percentage of recurrent hernias, with a total of 8 recurrences occurring during the follow-up period. The recurrence rate was generally low and did not show any significant differences based on the intervention

technique used for hernioplasty. Of particular interest, the TAPP-IRS technique demonstrated a positive outcome, as there was not a single case of hernia recurrence in the target group. The authors identified a significant increase in the recurrence rate of hernias among patients who were overweight and obese in the Liechtenstein group ($p=0.025$). The absence of any reported relapses (hernia recurrences) with TAPP-IRS is a noteworthy finding from the study. This indicates that TAPP-IRS was highly effective in preventing hernia recurrence in the patients who underwent this specific surgical approach. On the other hand, the Liechtenstein technique had the highest rate of hernia recurrence (Table 6).

This means that patients who underwent the Liechtenstein technique had a higher likelihood of experiencing hernia recurrence compared to other surgical methods used in the study. Furthermore, when TAPP was performed without IRS, the recurrence rate in this category was twice as high as the average for the entire group. This indicates that the addition of IRS in TAPP surgery played a significant role in reducing the risk of hernia recurrence.

Discussion

The selected clinical group in this study is characterized by excessive development of adipose tissue, especially on the anterior abdominal wall, leading to abdominal obesity and an increase in BMI. Moreover, the increased operational risk associated with open hernioplasty highlights the importance of adopting modern methods such as laparoscopic hernio-

Table 6. Data on the timing of recurrent inguinal hernia occurrence, categorized by the type of surgical intervention and the patients' body weight levels (measured in months)

Hernioplasty technique	Body weight		p-value
	Healthy	Overweight and obesity	
Shouldice, n=27	14±1	8±1	0.034
Liechtenstein, n=121	18±2	9±1.6	0.025
TAPP, n=98	-	7±1.4	-
TAPP-IRS, n=56	-	-	-
Average	14±2.1	8±1.5	0.069

Source: compiled by the authors.

plasty, particularly the TAPP approach. The use of TAPP and other advanced laparoscopic techniques significantly improves surgical outcomes for the treatment of inguinal hernias, as evidenced by various published studies.

Combining subgroups of patients with overweight and obesity is a common statistical practice when the number of obese patients is relatively small. By merging these subgroups, authors increased the sample size, which may improve the statistical power of the analysis and reduce the risk of obtaining non-significant results due to a limited number of participants in the obese category. When analysing the significance of the differences between the groups as a whole, the researchers found that there were statistically significant differences. This means that the higher incidence of complications in the overweight and obese groups was not just a chance occurrence but rather a meaningful and statistically significant finding. The findings of this study highlight the increased risk of complications in hernioplasty for individuals who are overweight or obese, particularly when using traditional methods like the Shouldice or Liechtenstein techniques. It underscores the importance of considering alternative approaches or techniques and individualizing the surgical approach based on the patients' BMI and overall health status to minimize postoperative complications in this specific population.

In comparison to A. Shakil et al. (2020), where seroma incidence for the TAPP group was in 14.7% of patients, in this study seroma incidences was close to 0.1%. Seroma formation is reduced in TAPP inguinal hernia repair due to specific procedural steps. Firstly, the peritoneum is excised circularly along the inner inguinal ring, establishing a foundation for mesh placement. However, the hernial sac is not entirely dissected to avoid harm to the gonadal vessels. During the suturing of the inner inguinal ring, the base of the hernial sac is incorporated. In contrast, with direct inguinal hernias, the hernial sac is fully separated from the base. When suturing the ring, the transverse fascia is engaged, completely closing the cavity and thus preventing the emergence of complications like seroma. However, results of this study are similar to A. Sultan et al. (2022), where the seroma formation was only 4% (2 patients out of 49) for the TAPP group. Regarding urinary retention, authors' findings are similar to Z. Jan et al. (2021), since in this study the incidence of urinary retention was 1.8%, in their study is only 4% for TAPP group, while for the Lichtenstein group it was 11% (in Z. Jan et al. (2021) only 22%). Swelling of the testicles, infiltration, suppuration is also low for TAPP-IRS group since the technique allows the prevention of the trauma and complete closure of the cavity to avoid any complications.

The effectiveness of the internal ring suturing technique used in TAPP-IRS is evident from the lack of reported pain syndrome (2022). By reinforcing the inguinal region and preventing hernia recurrence, the internal ring suturing likely played a crucial role in minimizing the risk of postoperative pain and chronic pain in hernia repair patients (2007). These findings underscore the potential benefits of TAPP-IRS as a reliable and successful surgical approach for inguinal hernia repair, not only in the short term but also in the prevention of long-term complications such as chronic pain. However, as with any study, further research and larger studies are

essential to validate and further investigate the long-term outcomes and advantages of TAPP-IRS in preventing chronic pain syndrome and improving patient outcomes.

TAPP-IRS was highly effective in preventing hernia recurrence, making it a valuable approach for patients at risk of hernia relapse. Individuals with higher body weight levels experienced a higher likelihood of hernia recurrence compared to those with normal body weight. The overall low rate of recurrent hernias and the success of TAPP-IRS in preventing recurrence are promising results and further support the use of laparoscopic techniques, especially TAPP-IRS, in hernia repair surgeries (2019). Nevertheless, larger studies and longer follow-up periods may be required to confirm these findings and validate the long-term effectiveness of different hernioplasty techniques in preventing hernia recurrence. This finding highlights the impact of overweight and obesity as risk factors for hernia recurrence. The excess weight puts additional strain on the repaired hernia site, potentially compromising the integrity of the repair and leading to a higher chance of hernia recurrence over time (Payiziwula et al, 2019). The results underscore the importance of considering patients' body weight and overall health status when planning hernia repair surgeries. Special attention and careful monitoring may be necessary for individuals with overweight and obesity to mitigate the risk of hernia recurrence and improve the long-term outcomes of the surgical intervention. In the TAPP-IRS group, there were no cases of hernia recurrence. The reason for this is the mesh implant migration. In the TAPP group without suturing, hernia recurrences occur more often, as the mesh implant migrates due to intra-abdominal pressure which leads to the hernia recurrence.

The study identified several significant factors influencing the development of hernia recurrence. These factors included:

Body Mass Index (BMI). BMI was another significant factor, with patients having an excess BMI (overweight or obese) being more prone to hernia recurrence compared to those with a normal BMI.

Method of Intervention. The choice between open and laparoscopic surgical techniques had a minimal effect on the risk of hernia recurrence. Notably, laparoscopic techniques, including TAPP-IRS, were associated with lower recurrence rates compared to open techniques.

This investigation had certain limitations. The observation period of 1 year provides short-term outcomes only; a longer period of assessment is a necessary next step. It is not uncommon for research publications to include a limited number of patients in the analysis, especially when studying specific surgical procedures and long-term outcomes. In this case, the study reported on a subset of operated patients who were followed up for a considerable period. However, the authors acknowledge the need for further research and an extension study to include a larger number of interventions and patients. By expanding the study and including more patients for each method of hernioplasty, researchers can gather more comprehensive data and increase the statistical power of the findings. This would allow for more robust analysis and more reliable conclusions regarding the effectiveness of the TAPP-IRS procedure and its long-term outcomes. It is commendable that the authors recognize the potential

for further research and plan to report on the outcomes of a larger number of interventions in the future. This ongoing research will provide valuable insights and contribute to the growing body of knowledge in the field of hernioplasty and the management of inguinal hernias.

Conclusions

Inguinal hernias are a common problem in medicine, and it is important to develop effective treatments for them. Determining which methods are most effective and safe for patients always remains relevant. The study included 302 patients diagnosed with primary inguinal hernias. The study used different surgical techniques, such as the Lichtenstein technique, the Shouldice technique, and the laparoscopic techniques using the TAPP approach, including the modified internal circumferential suture (TAPP-IRS) technique. The main purpose of the study was to determine the incidence and severity of chronic postoperative pain, the incidence of postoperative complications within a year, and the incidence of recurrent inguinal hernias within two years after surgery. The study allowed to investigate various surgical methods for treating inguinal hernias and compare their effectiveness and safety.

The study made it possible to compare different methods and determine which one has advantages or disadvantages over others. By choosing laparoscopic techniques such as TAPP, which surgeons can effectively address the problems associated with excess fat tissue and abdominal obesity in patients with inguinal hernias. These techniques provide improved results and better postoperative outcomes, making them the preferred choice for the treatment of inguinal hernias in patients with these clinical characteristics. The results show that the TAPP-IRS is very effective in preventing hernia recurrence compared with other methods, especially the Lichtenstein method. Internal circumferential closure with the TAPP-IRS appears to be a critical factor in reducing the risk of hernia recurrence and increasing the overall success of the hernia repair procedure.

References

- Bittner R, Arregui ME, Bisgaard T, et al. Guidelines for laparoscopic (TAPP) and endoscopic (TEP) treatment of inguinal Hernia [International Endohernia Society (IEHS)]. *Surgical Endoscopy*, 2011; 25(9):2773-2843.
- Castro GRA, Zilles A, Gazzola LD, et al. Laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair: The long-term assessment of chronic pain and quality of life. *Brazilian Archives of Digestive Surgery*, 2022; 35:e1695.
- Chan CK, Chan G. The Shouldice technique for the treatment of inguinal hernia. *Journal of Minimal Access Surgery*, 2006; 2(3), 124-128.
- Chowbey PK, Pithawala M, Khullar R, et al. Complications in groin hernia surgery and the way out. *Journal of Minimal Access Surgery*, 2006; 2(3):174-177.
- Decker E, Currie A, Baig MK. Prolene hernia system versus Lichtenstein repair for inguinal hernia: A meta-analysis. *Hernia*, 2019; 23(3):541-546.
- Fernando H, Garcia C, Hossack T, et al. Incidence, predictive factors and preventive measures for inguinal hernia following robotic and laparoscopic radical prostatectomy: A systematic review. *Journal of Urology*, 2019; 201(6):1072-1079.
- El Aal Sultan AA, Abo Elazm HA, Omran H. Lichtenstein versus transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) inguinal hernia repair for unilateral non recurrent hernia: A multicenter short term randomized comparative study of clinical outcomes. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, 2022; 76:103428.
- Jan Z, Ali S, Ahmed N, et al. Comparison of common postoperative complications between Lichtenstein open repair and laparoscopic transabdominal pre-peritoneal (TAPP) repair for unilateral inguinal hernia. *Cureus*, 2021; 13(9):e17863.
- Li J, Gong W, Liu Q. Intraoperative adjunctive techniques to reduce seroma formation in laparoscopic inguinal hernioplasty: A systematic review. *Hernia*, 2019; 23(4):723-731.
- Li B, Shi S, Qin C, et al. Internal ring defect closure technique in laparoscopic mesh hernioplasty for indirect inguinal hernia. *Frontiers in Surgery*, 2022; 9:794420.
- Mellert LT, Cheung ME, Zografakis JG, et al. Laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair using progrid self-fixating mesh: Technical learning curve and mid-term outcomes. *Surgical Technology International*, 2019; 34:235-240.
- Payiziwula J, Zhao P-J, Aierken A, et al. Laparoscopy versus open incarcerated inguinal hernia repair in octogenarians: Single-center experience with world review. *Surgical Laparoscopy, Endoscopy & Percutaneous Techniques*, 2019; 29(2): 138-140.
- Sakorafas GH, Halikias I, Nissotakis C, et al. Open tension free repair of inguinal hernias; The Lichtenstein technique. *BMC Surgery*, 2001; 1:3.
- Schmitz R, Willeke F, Barr J, et al. Robotic inguinal hernia repair (TAPP) first experience with the new Senhance Robotic System. *Surgical Technology International*, 2019; 34:243-249.
- Shakil A, Aparicio K, Barta E, et al. Inguinal hernias: Diagnosis and management. *American Family Physician*, 2020; 102(8):487-492.
- Sun P. Chapter 27 – Pain in the entire body. In: *The Management of Post-Operative Pain with Acupuncture 2007*; 175-180. London: Churchill Livingstone.
- Sun L, Shen YM, Chen J. Laparoscopic versus Lichtenstein hernioplasty for inguinal hernias: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Minimally Invasive Therapy & Allied Technologies*, 2020; 29(1):20-27.
- Tam V, Rogers DE, Al-Abbas A, et al. Robotic inguinal hernia repair: A large health system's experience with the first 300 cases and review of the literature. *Journal of Surgical Research*, 2019; 235:98-104.
- Townsend CM, Beauchamp RD, Evers BM, et al. *Sabiston textbook of surgery: The biological basis of modern surgical practice*. Philadelphia: Elsevier. 2012
- Vu JV, Gunaseelan V, Dimick JB, et al. Mechanisms of age and race differences in receiving minimally invasive inguinal hernia repair. *Surgical Endoscopy*, 2019; 33(12), 4032-4037.
- Wolak PK, Strzelecka A, Piotrowska-Gall A, et al. Percutaneous Internal Ring Suturing (PIRS) – The benefits of laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair. *Therapeutics and Clinical Risk Management*, 2022; 18:135-144.
- World Health Organization. 2010. A healthy lifestyle – WHO recommendations. <https://www.who.int/europe/news-room/fact-sheets/item/a-healthy-lifestyle---who-recommendations>.